

A GENERAL OVERVIEW OF THE NOTIONAL PARTS OF SPEECH IN ENGLISH AND AZERBAIJANI

Ismaili T.

*Azerbaijan, Nakhchivan State University
English teacher, Dr. of Ph.*

Abstract

The notional parts of speech are the main object of the article. The article states that since each language has different grammatical rules and laws, it becomes more interesting to conduct comparative researches. Because there are a lot of differences and similarities between languages. Based on the research object of typology, the article focuses on the similarities and differences between the notional parts of speech in English and Azerbaijani languages. The article aims to analyze the main parts of speech between two languages which belonging to different language families. A general comparative overview of nouns, adjectives, verbs, numerals, verbs and adverbs is the main goal of the article.

Keywords; notional parts, comparative researches, typology, morphology, inflectional and agglutinative languages.

Introduction. Morphology is a part of grammar. The object of morphology is the word and it studies the broad grammatical meanings of the word. Morphology covers all parts of speech. It learns the similarities and differences between them. Generally, comparative studies make interesting works. When we consider all this, we can see that some parts of speech are universal in all languages, including English and Azerbaijani. Almost all languages have nouns and verbs. In some cases, nouns refer to other words, but in general, nouns refer to the subject, and verbs refer to what is said about the subject. In English, the verb and its tense forms have many different characteristics from Azerbaijani [3]. These features of the main parts of speech, especially the verb, sometimes cause difficulties during the teaching of English grammar. When there is no equivalent of any concept in the mother tongue, it is necessary to look for certain ways for the target language learner to understand. English belongs to the group of Germanic languages of the Indo-European language family and is an inflectional language. Inflectional languages are languages that follow the root of the word. Internal inflection is also sometimes found in the English language both in the plural of the noun, "mouse" (mice) "mice" (mice) and in the past tenses of irregular verbs "write"-"wrote", "think"-"thought". Although each group has its own characteristics and peculiarities, they are interconnected and integrated. The Azerbaijani language belongs to the Oghuz group of Turkic languages and is an agglutinative language. Turkish, Finno-Ugric languages are considered such languages. For these languages, word correction and word change with suffixes are systematic, and the suffixes have the same functionality with a uniform classification and declension feature. In agglutinative languages, for example, in Azerbaijani, all word roots are independent lexical units, that is, independent words. No suffix is needed for the root to be a word. Figuratives, as a rule, are outside the word, that is, they are added to the word. The language groups to which it belongs indicate the differences between these two languages. The number of parts of speech in English and Azerbaijani languages is not the same. The number of main parts of speech in modern English is seven and in Azerbaijani it is six.

Nouns are words that denote the names of the various manifestations in our consciousness of all material beings that surround us. In the Azerbaijani language, plural nouns are formed with the suffix *lar*² (alma-alma-lar/apple-apples). In English, except for seven nouns that change their roots, others are formed with "s", "es" (flower-flowers). Special, general, concrete, abstract nouns are also exist in the Azerbaijani language. According to the structure of the noun, the simple, compound and compound types are almost the same. Unlike English, Azerbaijani does not have the concept of countable and uncountable. For example, the nouns bread, time, and money are not counted in English, but they are counted in Azerbaijani. In modern English, there are some nouns that are used in the plural form (tongs, scissors) [4]. Unlike in English, the nouns denoting these things in Azerbaijani language are used both in singular and plural according to the general rule like other nouns. For example, we use scissors, glasses, scales, etc. In contrast to the modern Azerbaijani language, the scope of processing the possessive case in English is much narrower. In English, as a rule, only nouns denoting living beings are used in the possessive case (my mother's birthday). As a rule, inanimate beings are expressed by the preposition "of" (the leg of the table). The noun has six cases in Azerbaijani and two cases in English. English and Azerbaijani languages do not have a special morphological form that can indicate the gender of the noun. In English, nouns are traditionally divided into masculine (masculine, feminine, neuter).

In English, the main criterion for dividing nouns into gender groups is their lexical meaning. There is generally no gender category in the Azerbaijani language [2]. Although there is no special indicator of gender in grammar, words such as poet, teacher, are used in the gender category in our language. According to academician N. Jafarov, this is a cultural event in the language[4]. According to him, the society should determine whether it is correct to use such words or not.

Adjective. German, Russian, etc. Unlike other languages, English does not have case, gender, and quantity categories of adjectives. Therefore, similarly in English and Azerbaijani languages, the adjective does

not agree with the noun it belongs to according to case, gender and quantity [4]. As in the Azerbaijani language, there are 3 types of adjectives and they are graded according to their structure. There is a degree of reduction and multiplication. The degree of reduction is fixed by means of certain suffixes (*imtirag-imtil*), and multiplication is also used by means of suffixes.

Numerals. In both languages, numerals refer to words that express the quantity or order of things. Fractions in English are very different from Azerbaijani. English uses both quantity and ordinal numbers. In the Azerbaijani language, the numerator is used in both the numerator and the denominator of the fraction. In English, the numerator consists of the numerator, and the denominator is the ordinal number (one fifth).

Pronoun. Each of the English personal pronouns in the object case corresponds to the 2 case forms of the personal pronoun in the Azerbaijani language - the indicative and the effective case forms. Unlike the Azerbaijani language, there are possessive pronouns that form a separate group in the English language. The form of English possessive pronouns used with a noun is usually translated into Azerbaijani through the possessive case form of personal pronouns. Subject relative pronouns in English are not translated into Azerbaijani. Complex sentences with definite clauses used in English are translated into Azerbaijani language in most cases by means of a simple long sentence. In contrast to the Azerbaijani language, there are binding pronouns in modern English [1]. The main characteristic of negative pronouns in English is that each of them expresses negation on its own. That is, when there is a negative pronoun, other negative means are not used in the sentence. But in the Azerbaijani language, there is also a second sign of negation in the sentence in which the negative pronoun is used.

Verb. Action and state words are called verbs. In both languages, the verb is a part of speech with complex properties. In English, a verb has the categories of person, quantity, tense, kind, manner, and form. Those categories are expressed in one case through suffixes, in the other case through auxiliary verbs. The tense forms of the news form of the verb in modern English are divided into 4 groups. 1) Indefinite tense forms 2) Continuous Tense Forms 3) Perfect Tense Forms 4) Perfect Continuous Tense Forms. Time is a broad and multifaceted concept. Time, which is a physical, philosophical, linguistic, and subjective-psychological phenomenon, can be studied from different perspectives. An objective universal phenomenon for the language system is that time, which is one of the main categories of reality, necessarily finds its expression at the conceptual level, that is, any extralinguistic experience of a person is realized in his mind through language means. The main feature that distinguishes the Azerbaijani language from the English language in terms of verbs is the presence of 3 tenses in the Azerbaijani language.

Time categories are one of the most challenging issues in foreign language teaching and translation. For example, the indefinite form of the present tense in Azerbaijani is usually translated by the present tense form of the verb. The indefinite form of the past tense corresponds to the past tense form of the verbs in Azerbaijani. In English, the future indefinite tense is translated by the future definite or future indefinite depending on the context.

Adverb. Just as there are qualities of things, there are qualities of actions and degrees of these qualities. Movement takes place within a certain time and space. Its occurrence has a cause, result, manner, etc. The words that serve to express the grammatical meanings related to those features inherent in the movement are called adverbs [6]. Adverbs in English can be classified in two ways. 1) according to their morphological structure 2) according to their meaning. As in the Azerbaijani language, the main function of the adverb in the English language is adverbiality.

The Conclusion

When considering the English language belonging to the inflectional language family and the Azerbaijani language belonging to the agglutinative language family, it can be observed that some parts of speech are universal in these two languages, as in all languages. For example, nouns refer to the subject and verbs refer to the person speaking about the subject. Regarding nouns, it can be noted that there are many similar categories of nouns in both languages. At the same time, different features of nouns in English, such as countable and uncountable, are also considered. In both languages, the verb is a part of speech with complex properties. But the category of time is a more complex and rich category in English. It can be noted that the main feature of adverbs in both languages is that they are mainly adverbial in the sentence. It should be noted that the difficulties faced by second language learners when learning grammar are caused by the differences between them.

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